

Name of Publisher: GO GREEN RESEARCH AND EDUCATION
Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review
Area of Publication: Business, Management and Accounting (miscellaneous)

Journal of Business and Management Research

Online ISSN

2958-5074

Print ISSN

2958-5066

Vol. 5, Issue. 1, 2026

MAPPING THE CONVERGENCE OF INDUSTRY 4.0 AND SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODELS: TRENDS, CLUSTERS, AND FUTURE PATHWAYS

Dr. Ammara Akram

Lecturer, Department of Commerce, Bahauddin Zakaria University Multan.

Email: ammara.akram@bzu.edu.pk

Muhammad Muzammil Masood

Department of Management Sciences Lahore Garrison University.

masoodmuzammil@ms.lgu.edu.pk

Nasir Abbas*

Lecturer, College of Commerce, Government College University, Faisalabad.

Corresponding Author Email: nasirabbas@gcuf.edu.pk.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-1711-2963>

Abstract

Purpose: This study maps the intellectual and thematic evolution of research at the convergence of Industry 4.0 and sustainable business models (SBMs), with a specific focus on business model-level mechanisms through which digital technologies support sustainability and circular value creation. **Design/methodology/approach-** A PRISMA-guided workflow was applied to construct a Scopus dataset comprising 391 journal articles during 2006-2026. Bibliometric performance analysis and science mapping were conducted using VOSviewer, including source analysis, document citation analysis, co-authorship networks, co-citation structures, and keyword co-occurrence mapping. **Findings:** Annual scientific production shows a sharp post-2020 acceleration, with 2021–2025 accounting for approximately 80% of publications and 2025 representing the peak year. The journal *Sustainability* (Switzerland) is the most prolific outlet, whereas the *Journal of Cleaner Production* is the most influential in terms of both citation impact and network centrality. Keyword analysis confirms a tightly coupled conceptual core around “Industry 4.0,” “sustainability/sustainable development,” and “circular economy,” with “digital transformation” and “business models” acting as bridging concepts. Document-level results indicate that field influence is shaped not only by highly cited works, but also by structurally embedded “bridge” papers exhibiting high total link strength. **Research limitations/implications-** The analysis is limited by Scopus coverage and term-based boundary decisions inherent to BM-centric corpus construction; bibliometric relationships indicate structural proximity rather than causal influence. Future work should extend multi-database coverage and deepen the empirical testing of I4.0-enabled SBM mechanisms, including ecosystem governance, capability development, and business model-level sustainability metrics. **Practical implications:** For managers, the results underscore the need to align I4.0 investments with explicit business model redesign (e.g., servitization, lifecycle traceability, and circular value networks). For policymakers, the findings highlight the importance of interoperability and data-governance infrastructures to enable scalable circular business models. **Originality/value:** By centring business models as the unit of analysis, this study provides a BM-focused science map of I4.0–sustainability convergence and identifies influential outlets, bridge documents, and an agenda for future SBM research.

Keywords-Industry 4.0; Sustainable business models; Circular economy; Circular business models; Digital transformation; Servitization; Bibliometric analysis; VOSviewer; PRISMA; Science mapping

1. Introduction

The concept of Industry 4.0 (I4.0), typically implemented by the cyber-physical networks, industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), cloud/edge computing, advanced analytics and artificial intelligence, digital twins, and automation, has become a new mainstream for reconfiguring production and value chains. Simultaneously, companies are experiencing growing pressure to achieve measurable sustainability performance, swiftly decarbonize, and overcome resource limitations, which has led to the increased popularity of sustainable business models (Sustainable business models) and circular economy (CE) strategies (ALSaoudi et al., 2026). Although these trajectories have often been discussed in parallel, a more consequential process is how they converge: digital technologies not only enhance operational efficiency but are increasingly being positioned to facilitate conditions to new value propositions, value creation architectures, and value capture

logics that incorporate both environmental, social value and economic value. Initial conceptual efforts openly claimed that I4.0 can facilitate sustainable business models through product longevity, repair, reuse, and recycling to alter customer relationships and financial justification, and not solely streamline operations (Man & Strandhagen, 2017). However, although scholarship on I4.0 and sustainability are growing rapidly, the intellectual and thematic framework of the research concentrating directly on the convergence of the business model level is diffuse.

The main causes of this diffusion are related areas such as sustainable manufacturing, sustainable supply chain management, circular operations, and digital transformation, which tend to take the center stage in the framing, with business model constructs being byproducts or management implications. Contributions to roadmaps and agenda setting have been highly cited in bringing together the I4.0–CE interface on sustainable operations (Jabbour et al., 2018) and in the definition of digitization as an enabler of CE transitions due to smarter asset utilization, lifecycle visibility, and data-driven optimization (Okorie et al., 2018). This overlap was further reinforced by other systematic reviews and bibliometric mappings that listed I4.0 technologies (e.g., Internet of Things, big data analytics, additive manufacturing, and blockchain) and placed them in the context of CE practices and sustainability objectives (Ćwiklicki & Wojnarowska, 2020; Patyal et al., 2022). However, in much of this literature, sustainable and circular business models are often discussed as components of larger sustainability or supply-chain stories, and not as the unit of analysis. Consequently, it is still difficult to identify which business model archetypes, mechanisms, and governance issues are the most central and least studied in the I4.0-enabled sustainability transition.

Several common mechanisms have been proposed in the literature as to how I4.0 can be converted into a sustainable or circular business model innovation. First, digital servitization and product-service systems (PSS) are frequently referred to as bridging concepts: connectivity and remote monitoring allow usage-based, outcome-based, or performance-based propositions that could decouple revenue and material throughput and uphold product-life extension schemes (Atif et al., 2021; Nirmal et al., 2025). Second, sensors, data platforms, and analytics make visibility and traceability throughout product lifecycles possible, which is presented as a requirement of closed-loop supply chains, reverse logistics, and remanufacturing pathways (Gupta et al., 2025). Third, an emergent stream focuses on ecosystems and platforms as the place of circular value creation coordination among many actors, suggesting the emergence of new partnership forms and data regulation solutions outside of the central company (Alka et al., 2024; Gorokhova et al., 2024). Notably, these mechanisms are business model relevant: they directly involve value proposition design (e.g., product-as-a-service), value creation and delivery architecture (e.g., take-back systems coordinated digitally), and value capture (e.g., subscription, pay-per-use, or outcome contracts).

This conceptual energy has not prevented the field from being marked by fragmentation at the levels of its range, definition, and analysis. General mappings of I4.0 and sustainable development are heavily focused on the adoption and implementation of technologies and present the themes of CE and sustainable business models as new ones (Khan et al., 2021). Similarly, a bibliometric analysis of I4.0 and sustainability issues demonstrates several clusters, including smart manufacturing, a circular economy, sustainable supply chains, and business models, but also identifies technology-focused

trends and the lack of balance in discussing sustainability constructs (Ejmsont et al., 2020). Targeted reviews on I4.0–CE integration also affirm its growth yet emphasize that empirical data on its adoption and implementation are still rather new and that conceptual frameworks frequently surpass business model designs that have proven to be effective (Sahu et al., 2021; Silva & Sehnem, 2022). More recent work expands the discussion to include twin transformation (digitalization and sustainability) and capabilities, suggesting structured technology pictures and research gaps to manufacturing situations (Bühler et al., 2025) and defining the skills needed to leverage I4.0 to circular economy business models (Anshari & Pablos, 2025). However, despite a shift in the focus of specialized bibliometric studies of digital technologies in CE towards policy tools and data-driven transparency (Le-Dinh et al., 2025), the extent to which and how the business model lens is influencing the core and frontiers of the field is not clear.

This study addresses this gap by offering a PRISMA-guided bibliometric analysis and science mapping of the literature that specifically deals with the convergence between Industry 4.0 and sustainable business models, in which trends, clusters, and changing research fronts are determined with the help of VOSviewer. The differentiating assumption is that a business-model-based mapping needs not only to co-mention the terms I4.0 and sustainability but must be systematically delimited around business model constructs (e.g., SBM/CBM, business model innovation, servitization/PSS) and articulate the way digital technologies change value logic. Two observations drive this positioning within the landscape of extant reviews. First, while several studies map the links among I4.0, CE, and sustainability (Patyal et al., 2022; Silva & Sehnem, 2022), many are anchored at the operations or supply chain level, leaving business model archetypes less differentiated. Second, where business models are addressed, they are often described as outcomes of CE strategy implementation; for example, CE strategies (including “digital technologies such as Industry 4.0”) can influence business model building blocks, especially customer relationships and partnerships, suggesting that business model change is central rather than incidental (Salvador et al., 2021). Therefore, this study consolidates dispersed contributions into an interpretable intellectual structure that is explicitly filtered and interpreted through a business model lens.

Accordingly, this study is guided by the following research questions. RQ1 (trend and performance) asks how the I4.0–SBM convergence literature has developed over time in terms of publication growth, influential outlets, leading authors, institutions, and geographic contributions. RQ2 (thematic clustering) asks what major thematic clusters can be identified through keyword co-occurrence mapping and how these clusters correspond to business-model-relevant mechanisms (e.g., servitization, traceability, platformization, remanufacturing, or reverse-loop configurations). RQ3 (intellectual foundations) asks which works and knowledge bases form the field’s intellectual core, as evidenced by co-citation structures, and how these foundations relate to agenda-setting contributions in I4.0-enabled CE and business model innovation. RQ4 (evolution and emerging themes) asks which topics appear to be emerging at the research frontier via overlay visualizations and bibliographic coupling, with particular attention to recent emphases on capabilities, and “twin transformation” framings. Finally, RQ5 (future pathways) synthesizes cluster gaps into a forward-looking agenda that prioritizes empirically testable pathways for business model innovation under I4.0-enabled sustainability transitions, including measurement and performance evaluation challenges

that remain salient across reviews.

The contribution of this study provides a clear and reproducible methodology for PRISMA-directed dataset creation and cleaning, alongside VOSviewer-driven mapping, which would be appropriate for researchers interested in benchmarking or expanding science maps in the field. Second, at the conceptual level, the work offers a business model-based explanation of clusters that are recurrently observed but not always described regarding the logic of value creation and capture (e.g., the so-called repetitively observed technology-circularity-business model triad prevalent in the scope of larger mappings, (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021). Third, on the agenda-setting level, the study condenses future directions in the form of (i) I4.0-enabled digital servitization of circularity, (ii) data governance and ecosystem coordination of circular platforms, (iii) organizational capabilities and skills of twin transformation, and (iv) metrics of linking particular technology applications to SBM outcomes, both environmental and social, which are typically unevenly covered by practice and the literature.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the conceptual background by delving into the theoretical processes behind the interrelation of Industry 4.0 (I4.0) technologies and sustainable business models (SBMs) and the creation of circular value. Section 3 The methodology based on PRISMA, such as data gathering, screening criteria, and the settings of VOSviewer that were used to conduct the bibliometric analysis. Section 4 presents the findings on publication patterns, collaboration patterns, thematic patterns, and time patterns. These findings are discussed in Section 5 with the aim of refining the existing knowledge about I4.0-enabled SBM innovation, identifying the shifts in business model-centric approaches and research pathways that can be used to address the synthesized literature gaps; finally, Section 6 concludes the study and discusses its theoretical and managerial implications, as well as future empirical research directions.

2. Conceptual Background

Research on the interface of Industry 4.0 (I4.0) and sustainable business models (SBMs) has grown at a blistering pace; however, the academic field is not conceptually homogeneous. Therefore, there is a need to develop a brief conceptual framework that will allow us to interpret bibliometric patterns (clusters, centrality, overlays through time) in a manner that is true to business model theory, without reducing the subject matter to generic digitalization or sustainability statements. This section outlines the focal constructs, followed by a synthesis of the mechanism of business model level that is plausible to explain the presence of specific keywords, outlets, and citations that recurrently appear within the literature.

2.1. Core Constructs and Boundary Conditions

The 4.0 industry as a value-generation infrastructure

I4.0-sustainability literature, I4.0 is generally operationalized as a collection of enabling technologies (e.g., Internet of Things/IIoT, cyber-physical systems, cloud/edge infrastructure, advanced analytics/AI, digital twins, additive manufacturing, and blockchain) that make operations and supply chains more connected, more data-enabled, and automated (Anna et al., 2025; Ejsmont et al., 2020; Shabur, 2024). When it comes to business model analysis, it is important to note that I4.0 is not an end-state (but it is an infrastructure of capabilities, mostly datafication and connectivity). The redesign of value propositions, value creation and delivery, and value capture determine whether these

capabilities result in sustainable value (Polo et al., 2025).

Sustainable Circular Business Models

Sustainable business models expand the unit of value to encompass not only economic value, but specifically the creation and distribution of environmental and social value. Within the CE framework, the concept of sustainable value is often operationalized using circular strategies to reduce, decelerate, and recycle resource loops (e.g., reuse, repair, remanufacturing, recycling, and sharing) (Patyal et al., 2022; Salvador et al., 2021). Notably, CE strategies are not operational practices; usually, they are new revenue logics (e.g., pay-per-use and performance contracts) and other forms of partnerships (e.g., take-back ecosystems), as well as new governance of data and responsibilities along the lifecycle. This is why business model constructs are recurrently evident as an interpretive linkage amid I4.0 technologies and CE results (Hadi et al., 2025).

Boundary condition: distinguishing business model convergence from “green manufacturing” optimization

A recurrent limitation in the broader I4.0–sustainability corpus is the dominance of process-level optimization (energy efficiency, scheduling, and predictive maintenance) that may improve environmental performance without materially changing value capture or customer relationships (Ng et al., 2022). Because this study maps the convergence between I4.0 and sustainable business models, the conceptual focus is the set of mechanisms through which digital capabilities enable business model-level circularity and sustainability, including changes in revenue models, customer engagement, lifecycle responsibility, and cross-firm coordination.

2.2. Mechanisms linking Industry 4.0 to sustainable/circular business models

The literature repeatedly converges on a limited set of mechanisms that are both business model relevant and empirically tractable. These mechanisms provide a basis for interpreting bibliometric clusters as more than semantic groupings.

2.2.1. Digital servitization and product–service systems (PSS) as circular value propositions

A foundational claim is that I4.0 enables servitization, the shift from selling products to providing services or outcomes, by making assets monitorable, updatable, and optimizable in use. Connectivity (Internet of Things/IIoT), remote diagnostics, and analytics allow firms to offer uptime guarantees, performance-based contracts, predictive maintenance services, and pay-per-use arrangements (Atif, 2023; Strandhagen et al., 2017). From a circularity perspective, servitization can support “slowing loops” by extending product life (maintenance, repair, and refurbishment) and incentivizing durability when ownership and lifecycle performance are tied to provider revenue (Man & Strandhagen, 2017). Hence, in SBM-centric mappings, terms such as servitization, product–service systems, outcome-based, pay-per-use, and digital services are expected to form bridging nodes between technology-focused and circularity-focused clusters (Gorokhova et al., 2024).

2.2.2. Visibility, traceability, and lifecycle intelligence enabling closed-loop architectures

A second widely cited mechanism is that I4.0 enables CE implementation by providing lifecycle data conditions, location, usage history, and configuration that support reverse logistics, remanufacturing, reuse, and higher-quality recycling decisions (Bai et al., 2022; Jabbour et al., 2018). For business model design, lifecycle intelligence affects the

following: Value proposition: guarantees of provenance, verified circular content, or performance supported by real-time data. Value creation/delivery: orchestration of take-back systems, inspection triage, remanufacturing planning, and inventorying of returned cores. Value capture: Monetization through secondary markets, service contracts, or data-enabled differentiation.

Review-based evidence suggests that these dynamics are frequently analyzed through CE action frameworks, in which “share/optimize” and life-extension actions are often linked to digital monitoring and analytics (Ćwiklicki & Wojnarowska, 2020; Patyal et al., 2022). As a result, bibliometric datasets that include CE frameworks typically show strong co-occurrence among IoT, big data, traceability, reverse logistics, remanufacturing, and closed-loop supply chain themes (Agrawal et al., 2021; Das et al., 2024).

2.2.3. Platformization and ecosystem orchestration as multi-actor business model innovation

Circular value creation often involves coordination between manufacturers, customers, logistics, repair, remanufacturers, and recyclers. With the reduction of coordination costs and increased information disclosure with digitalization, multiple recent strands have highlighted platforms and ecosystems as business model architectures towards circularity, especially where value is co-created between actors and mediated by data and digital interfaces (Alka et al., 2024; Gorokhova et al., 2024). Under this framing, I4.0 would also reposition the locus of SBM innovation not at the firm-level redesign, but at the ecosystem-level orchestration, which raises the following questions: Governance and incentives: the way value is shared among participants in the ecosystem. Data control: rights, standards, interoperability, and trust. Market design: marketplace models of sharing, secondary markets, and service marketplace models.

Even though the evidence base is yet to be consolidated, this ecosystem perspective can be used to justify the increasing appearance of such terms as platform, ecosystem, value co-creation, and sharing economy, next to more traditional I4.0 and CE keywords (Yadav et al., 2026). The above also implies that business model clusters can be servitization-centric as well as platform-centric.

2.2.4. Strategic and organizational capabilities as enabling conditions for “twin transformation”

A fourth mechanism is the ability of the firm: although digital technologies and CE technologies exist, organizations might not adopt sustainable business models because of data, governance, and cross-functional integration gaps in their capabilities. Capability-focused reviews refer to the concept of dynamic capabilities: sensing, seizing, and transforming, and bring CE and I4.0 together in the context of supply chains and operational routines (Lu et al., 2024). Accordingly, the framing of twin transformation shows that the goals of digitalization and sustainability should be co-designed and not pursued in a linear manner, emphasizing the importance of organizational learning, skills, and decision-making structures (Anshari & Pablos, 2025; Bühler et al., 2025).

In theory, this process would mean that bibliometric clusters can be organized around: Constructs of capability: dynamic capabilities, absorptive capacity, ambidexterity, and organizational readiness. Human capital: skills, training, talent, and change management. Obstacles to implementation: cybersecurity, data integration, investment justification, and resistance to change. Such themes are particularly topical when the research frontier is changed to not be about which technologies will make the world go

round. to "what organizational capabilities can scale-IC-enabled Sustainable business models (Buhler et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2024).

2.2.5. Business model building blocks and reconfiguration logic

Finally, SBM convergence can be viewed in the business model elements. CE business model research findings show that digital technologies (explicitly, I4.0) are among the approaches demonstrating helpfulness in business model design, specifically, customer-facing blocks and the structure of partnerships (Salvador et al., 2021). This should be taken to justify a particular analytic position of the bibliometric interpretation, that is, keywords associated with customers and relationships (e.g., customer engagement, co-creation), partnerships (e.g., supply chain collaboration), and revenue models (e.g., subscription, pay-per-use) are not peripheral; the latter may be the mechanistic interface that I4.0 generates sustainable value. As a result, a BM-centric mapping can be anticipated to place these terms higher than the broader I4.0-sustainability corpora, in which the process terms can prevail (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Ng et al., 2022).

2.3. Expected bibliometric “signals” and interpretive expectations

The conceptual mechanisms described above imply several recurring bibliometric structures that can be used as interpretive expectations.

Many broad mappings of I4.0–sustainability and I4.0–CE show clusters that align with (i) digital technologies, (ii) circularity/sustainability practices, and (iii) business model/servitization themes, with bridging terms connecting them (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Das et al., 2024). In SBM-centric datasets, the “business model” pole should become more central and internally differentiated (e.g., servitization versus platforms). Co-citation structures are expected to highlight agenda-setting and integrative works that frame I4.0 as enabling CE and sustainable business models, such as research agenda pieces on sustainable business models under I4.0 (Man & Strandhagen, 2017), roadmaps for I4.0–CE integration (Jabbour et al., 2018), digitization–CE synthesis emphasizing data-driven circularity (Okorie et al., 2018), bibliometric baselines mapping I4.0 and sustainability (Ejsmont et al., 2020), and I4.0 and sustainable development via CE/sustainable business models (Khan et al., 2021).

The field’s evolution suggests an early emphasis on I4.0 and sustainable operations, followed by growth in themes such as servitization/PSS, ecosystems/platforms, skills, and twin transformation (Atif et al., 2021; Bühler et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2024). If present, these overlays strengthen the interpretation that the research frontier is moving toward the implementation and scaling of sustainable business models rather than cataloguing technologies. In summary, this conceptual framing treats I4.0 as a capability substrate and CBMs as reconfigurations of value logic, linked through identifiable mechanisms (servitization, lifecycle intelligence, ecosystem orchestration, and capabilities). These mechanisms provide disciplined lenses for interpreting bibliometric clusters and for translating science maps into a future research agenda focused on business model innovation rather than purely technical or process-level sustainability.

3. Methods

3.1. Research Design Overview

The present study employs a PRISMA-based bibliometric research design, which involves (a) performance analysis (descriptive and impact measures) and (b) science mapping (network-based structure discovery) (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). The task is not

to assess the substantive quality of the studies, but to trace the organization of the research area on the topic of Industry 4.0-enabled sustainable business models, its development, and the domination of thematic and intellectual prevailing structures. This method is based on traditional bibliometric practice that confines itself to descriptive indicators (e.g., growth, productivity, impact) and relational indicators, which demonstrate structural patterns (e.g., co-occurrence and co-citation networks) (Donthu et al., 2021).

3.2. Data source and rationale

Scopus is used to retrieve bibliographic datasets. Numerous studies use Scopus in bibliometric research because of its wide coverage of journals and well-organized metadata (authors, affiliations, abstracts, keywords, and cited reference) that can be used in network analysis and cleaning processes. In recent studies, Scopus-only designs are typically used in the domain mapping of digitalization–circular economy and I4.0–sustainability intersections, and VOSviewer is often additionally used to network and cluster keywords (e.g., Anna et al., 2025; Duarte et al., 2024; Patyal et al., 2022; Le-Dinh et al., 2025).

3.3. Search strategy and query development (replicability)

A structured search query was developed to identify the business-model-level convergence between I4.0 and sustainability/circularity. In line with the study’s scope, the query will necessitate the combination of (i) the I4.0/digitalization concept and (ii) the SBM/CBM/business-model innovation concept, as opposed to superficial co-mention.

The last query was executed in Scopus on the field of TITLE-ABS-KEY. The keyword constructions are in three families:

Industry 4.0 / digitalization family (e.g., “Industry 4.0,” “smart manufacturing,” “industrial Internet of Things,” “cyber-physical,” “digital twin,” “big data,” “artificial intelligence,” “blockchain”). Business model family (e.g., “business model,” “business model innovation,” “value proposition,” “value creation,” “value capture,” “servitization,” “product-service system”). Sustainability/circularity family (e.g., “sustainable,” “sustainable business model,” “circular business model,” “circular economy,” “closed loop,” “remanufacturing,” “reverse logistics”).

3.4. Screening and eligibility: PRISMA workflow

PRISMA 2020 was applied to identify studies, screen them, and include them (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021). PRISMA flow diagrams indicate the records at both levels (identification, deduplication, screening, eligibility, and final inclusion) and the primary reasons for exclusion at full-text eligibility where used.

Inclusion criteria:

This paper specifically deals with Industry 4.0 (or related concepts of digital/smart manufacturing) and examines business model constructs (SBM, CBM, servitization/PSS, BMI, or explicit value proposition/creation/capture redesign). The research substantively discusses the mechanisms connecting I4.0 technologies to sustainability/circular value logic (not just process optimization).

Exclusion criteria:

Technical I4.0 research where sustainability is only a generic motivation or performance metric. Sustainability/CE papers that remain at the macro policy/territorial levels without business model analysis. Papers that only list I4.0 and sustainability as parallel trends without articulating their integration at the business model level

Figure| 01 PRISMA Diagram

3.5. Data export and preprocessing

Records were exported from Scopus with full bibliographic fields needed for VOSviewer analyses, including authors, affiliations, titles, abstracts, author keywords, index keywords (where available), sources (journals/conferences), citations, and cited references.

A two-stage preprocessing protocol was applied:

1. **Deduplication and basic validation** (consistent publication identifiers and removal of incomplete entries).
2. **Normalization of terms** using a VOSviewer thesaurus file (e.g., harmonizing variants such as “servitization/sovietisation”; “Industry 4.0/Industrie 4.0”; “product-service system/PSS”; and singular/plural forms). Keyword cleaning also removes non-informative terms (e.g., “study,” “framework”) and ambiguous acronyms where expansion is uncertain.

3.6. Bibliometric analyses and VOSviewer configuration

All science maps were generated using **VOSviewer**, a widely adopted tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010). The study employs complementary network types to triangulate the field's structure:

Keyword co-occurrence analysis (author keywords; optionally supplemented with index keywords) to reveal thematic clusters and bridging concepts across I4.0, sustainability, and business model logic. Co-authorship networks (countries and/or institutions) to characterize collaboration patterns. We conduct co-citation analysis (identified by the cited references and/or sources) to identify the intellectual foundations of the field, including agenda-setting works linking I4.0 to circularity and sustainable business models (Man & Strandhagen, 2017; Jabbour et al., 2018; Okorie et al., 2018; Ejsmont et al., 2020). Bibliographic coupling (documents and/or sources) can capture the research front and emerging thematic areas, particularly useful in fast-growing fields where citation accumulation lags (Das et al., 2024; Le-Dinh et al., 2025).

3.7. Robustness and sensitivity checks

To reduce dependence on arbitrary parameter choices, this study performed sensitivity checks by varying (a) keyword occurrence thresholds and (b) inclusion of index keywords versus author keywords only. Cluster stability was assessed by comparing whether the core cluster themes persisted under these alternative specifications. Where cluster interpretation is uncertain, this study cross-validates it using bibliographic coupling and co-citation patterns.

3.8. Biases, restrictions, and ethical implications

The design has inherent bibliometric drawbacks: (i) bias of the database coverage (Scopus-only), (ii) bias of language and document-type filters (when applied), (iii) bias within the time lag of citation (towards older publications), and (iv) bias of the term-based boundaries (especially when the search terms are business model and servitization). These shortcomings are addressed as interpretative constraints and not as methodological failures and are revisited in the process of discussing findings and the research agenda.

4. Bibliometric Analysis

4.1. Annual Scientific Production

In Figure 2, latency in annual scientific production, which is followed by a sharp rise after 2020--evidence of which was already found in prior reviews and that the I4.0 circularity--sustainability interface was consolidated in the early 2020s (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Patyal et al., 2022; Das et al., 2024). Empirically, there is a thin body of work to 2018 (1–5 articles/year, 2015–2017; 9 in 2018; 23 in 2019). This is followed by an increase in production in 2020 (26), a consistently high volume in 2021 (51), 2022 (49), and 2023 (59), and a high point in the dataset in 2025 (87 articles). As of March 29, 2026 (partial-year count), year 2026 will have 10 articles, and thus should not be seen as a decrease in the underlying publication activity.

In general, this BM-centric delimitation is robustly recent: 2021-2025 is home to 313 out of 391 articles (80%); therefore, explicit convergence of business models at the level of I4.0 and sustainability/circularity is certainly a research area that is growing fast but is not well established yet. This trend is consistent with more recent second-generation syntheses, which document topic specialization and diversification of mechanisms, including data-driven circularity and servitization, and policy themes of governance/policy in the mid-2020s (Le-Dinh et al., 2025; Buhler et al., 2025).

Figure 02: Annual Scientific Production

Table 01: Annual Scientific Production

YEAR	Annual Scientific Production
2026	10
2025	87
2024	67
2023	59
2022	49
2021	51
2020	26
2019	23
2018	9
2017	5
2016	1
2015	3
2006	1

4.2 Top Sources

Source analysis, presented in Table 2 and Figures 3 and 4, reveals that the literature is concentrated in the outlets of sustainability, cleaner production, and environmental and technology management. Sustainability (Switzerland) is the most active outlet (38 articles), and the Journal of Cleaner Production is the most powerful in terms of citations (3, 739) and technology and society laboratories (3,156), proving its centrality in the journal net of the given field. Business Strategy and the Environment and Technological Forecasting and Social Change are also identified as core sources, representing the strategic and foresight-oriented definitions of I4.0-enabled sustainability and business model change.

Table 2: Top Ten Sources by Documents, Citations, and Total Link Strength

Rank	Source	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
1	Sustainability (Switzerland)	38	3,132	2,334

Rank	Source	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
2	Journal of Cleaner Production	23	3,739	3,156
3	Business Strategy and the Environment	14	1,011	1,978
4	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	11	988	1,359
5	Computers & Industrial Engineering	7	1,202	1,232
6	Annals of Operations Research	7	1,175	887
7	Journal of Environmental Management	6	784	838
8	Systems	5	682	299
9	Journal of Self-Governance and Management Economics	4	209	29
10	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	4	175	351

Figure 03

Figure 04

4.3 Top Authors

Author-level performance brings a more focused group of prolific contributors and impact, and network position does not necessarily correlate with the number of publications, as shown in Table 3 and Figures 5 and 6. The most active author is Sachin Kumar Mangla (five articles). Judit Olah is distinguished by the citation impact (984 citations in 4 articles). Charbel Jose Chiappetta Jabbour has the highest TLS (1,640), which is in line with his central bridging position in the co-authorship structure and cross-cluster connectivity (van Eck and Waltman, 2010).

Table 3: Top Ten Authors by Documents, Citations, and Total Link Strength

Rank	Author	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
1	Mangla, Sachin Kumar	5	237	1,104
2	Olah, Judit	4	984	602
3	Chiappetta Jabbour, Charbel Jose	4	293	1,640
4	Popp, József	3	982	576
5	Khan, Syed Abdul Rehman	3	615	933
6	Ferrari, Anna Maria	3	502	705
7	Kumar, Ajay	3	318	936
8	Lopes de Sousa Jabbour, Ana Beatriz	3	274	1,111
9	Alkaraan, Fadi	3	241	1,163
10	Elmarzouky, Mahmoud	3	241	0

Figure 05

Figure 06

4.4. Top Affiliations

Geographic performance in institutional performance is observed when some institutions play a small role in terms of volume but exert high levels of influence via citations or collaboration relationships, as shown in Table X and Figures 8 and 9. The most prolific institutions are the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (Department of Sciences and Methods to Engineering) and the University of Glasgow (Adam Smith Business School) (three articles each). The University of Debrecen (Institute of Applied

Informatics and Logistics) has the best impact (966 citations and two articles). There are also some institutions that have a high collaboration connectivity (e.g. Ilma University and Chang'an University each with TLS 1,011) or i.e. a high cross-institutional co-authorship linkage.

Table 4: Top Ten Affiliations by Documents, Citations, and Total Link Strength

Rank	Organization	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
1	Dept. of Sciences and Methods for Engineering, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (Italy)	3	502	730
2	Adam Smith Business School, University of Glasgow (UK)	3	396	783
3	School of Expertness and Valuation, Institute of Technology and Business (Czech Republic)	3	198	47
4	Institute of Applied Informatics and Logistics, University of Debrecen (Hungary)	2	966	898
5	Department of Business Administration, Ilma University (Pakistan)	2	519	1,011
6	School of Economics and Management, Chang'an University (China)	2	519	1,011
7	Cadi Ayyad University (Morocco)	2	341	378
8	Gruppo Ceramiche Gresmalt, Sassuolo (Italy)	2	328	539
9	School of Economics and Business, University of Technology (Lithuania)	2	315	719
10	Dept. of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, Politecnico di Milano (Italy)	2	246	386

Figure 07

Figure 08

4.5. Top Countries and Global Research Hubs

At the country level, a well-knit international research community is observed. India serves as the leading center in all indicators (dominating in documents (68), citations (4,923), and TLS (27,183)), implying its high productivity, as well as centrality in the networks of international collaboration (van Eck & Waltman, 2010), as shown in Table V

and Figures 9 and 10. The next level of significant contributors is represented by China (51 documents) and the United Kingdom (49 documents). Italy has a high impact (3,534 citations and 32 documents), which means that it has a high citation intensity in comparison to the output volume.

Table 5: Top Ten Countries by Documents, Citations, and Total Link Strength

Rank	Country	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
1	India	68	4,923	27,183
2	China	51	2,409	14,193
3	United Kingdom	49	2,931	18,367
4	Italy	32	3,534	11,558
5	Spain	27	1,801	5,372
6	United States	23	1,832	10,384
7	Brazil	23	1,634	6,145
8	Australia	20	971	8,857
9	France	19	2,453	11,777
10	Malaysia	19	443	4,997

Figure 09

Figure 10

4.6 Top Documents

An analysis of document citations points to a thinly knit intellectual core featuring contributions to I4.0, sustainability, and circularity, as shown in Table VI and Figures 11 and 12. The dataset has the most significant number of citations for Lopes de Sousa Jabbour (2018) (973), Manavalan (2019) (913), and Esmaeilian (2020) (791). Notably, citation impact and network position are not entirely congruent: Javaid (2022) has the highest TLS (405) among the top documents, indicating a prominent bridging role across the bibliographic coupling or co-citation framework, and Fatimah (2020) has a high citation impact but an incredibly low TLS, indicating a relatively weak integration as a network core.

Table 6: Top Ten Documents by Citations and Total Link Strength

Rank	Document	Citations	Total link strength
1	Lopes de Sousa Jabbour (2018)	973	145
2	Manavalan (2019)	913	175
3	Esmaeilian (2020)	791	95
4	Javaid (2022)	762	405
5	Fatimah (2020)	592	4
6	Nagy (2018)	526	78
7	Oláh (2020)	440	100
8	Norouzi (2021)	416	48
9	Khan (2021)	383	134
10	Bag (2021)	382	207

Figure 11

Figure 12

4.7. Co-authorship Analysis

The mapping of co-authorship also proposes a collaborative topology of several integrating subgroups over one compact global network of authors, which is in line with the rapid growth and diversification of the field in terms of themes, as shown in Figure 13. Sachin Kumar Mangla is the most prolific author in this co-authorship setup (5 documents). Judit Olah has the greatest impact on citation (984 citations in 4 documents). The TLS of co-authorship between Fadi Alkaraan and Mahmoud Elmarzouky is the greatest (13), which indicates the presence of active collaboration in the cluster. (Note that TLS in co-author networks cannot be compared to TLS in co-citation networks or source networks because they are based on different relational data structures).

Figure 13

4.8. Co-Citation: Intellectual Foundations

VOSviewer analysis was performed using a co-citation (sources, cited references, and cited authors) approach to determine the intellectual foundation of the field, with common co-citation suggesting the existence of similar conceptual ancestry and thematic closeness (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). The results are offered qualitatively based on the observed network structure because the exports did not include numerical co-citation tables (citations and TLS of each co-cited unit), meaning that the results were summarized based on the observed network.

Co-cited sources (journals):

A core of production/operations and cleaner production (usually based on journals such as the Journal of Cleaner Production and frontline production/operations journals), representing the operations and supply-chain lens that is typical of I4.0-circularity studies. Resource-loop governing and technology-forecasting journals have emerged (often referred to as technology/innovation and resource-management core), indicating the mechanisms of digital transformation and the resource loop. A sustainability core (frequently based on Sustainability) that represents general sustainability frames and multidimensional performance agendas.

Figure 14

Co-Cited References and Authors

focus on popular integrative frames linking I4.0 technologies to sustainability/circular economy transitions, which is in keeping with the high percentage of overlap among the most-cited documents as well as the prevalence of "Industry 4.0" as a keyword and the semantic words sustainability/sustainable development and circular economy at the center of the keyword web (van Eck & Waltman, 2010).

Figure 15

Figure 16

4.9. Keyword Co-Occurrence: Core Themes and Cluster Interpretation

The comparison of keyword co-occurrence reveals that the domain is structured around a small set of concepts with high frequency and connection. Industry 4.0, with the most presence (232 times; TLS 1, 157), is closely related to sustainability-oriented terms, including "sustainable development" (119; TLS 812) and sustainability (113; TLS 654). Circularity is structurally focal, where the vocabulary of technology is linked to sustainability by the term "circular economy" (79; TLS 425). The terms with the most occurrences are business-model language (28 instances) and digital transformation (39 instances), which seems to be a major connection point between technology and managerial change. As the cluster IDs (colour/group membership) were not included in the export statistics table, the cluster names below are reported as a theory-consistent interpretation, as that is expected to be seen in this area (technology-sustainability/circularity-operations/strategy) and should be interpreted as an interpretive grouping, as opposed to a precise recreation of VOSviewer cluster assignments.

Table 7: Top Ten Keywords by Occurrences and Total Link Strength

Rank	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
1	Industry 4.0	232	1,157
2	Sustainable development	119	812
3	Sustainability	113	654
4	Circular economy	79	425
5	Digital transformation	39	149
6	Manufacturing	36	259
7	Innovation	32	194
8	Supply chains	31	234

conclusion: within this field, the innovation of the business model is often operationalized with references to the contexts of production, supply chain, and industrial systems, which cannot be reduced solely to the strategy or entrepreneurship perspective. This aligns with the general bibliometric mappings of Industry 4.0 and sustainability, indicating high levels of operations and supply chain grounding, yet still identifying business model clusters as a recognizable thematic element (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021). The current BM-based delimitation seems to compound this by continuing studies in which value creation/capture is being discussed, but in which the empirical locus is still manufacturing and supply chains.

5.2. Source dominance and what it implies about the field's "knowledge regime"

In source analysis, there is a two-mode publication regime: (a) high-throughput sustainability outlets and (b) highly central integrative outlets, which form the conceptual core of the field. The very high centrality of the *Journal of Cleaner Production*, both in terms of citation impact and network strength, suggests that the knowledge base is highly influenced by the so-called solution-oriented sustainability scholarship that relates environmental goals to operational and managerial processes (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017; van Eck and Waltman, 2010). Meanwhile, high productivity in Sustainability (Switzerland) indicates a wide and rapid publication channel that encompasses a variety of approaches, settings, and sectoral situations.

This convergence has a theoretical upshot: the I4.0-SBM field is coming together around the idea of integrative and interdisciplinary framing; however, the range of publication outlets also indicates that the definition of concepts and units of analysis is still diverse. This aligns with previous reviews that identified fragmentation and imprecision of concepts in the I4.0-sustainability literature, particularly when sustainability is regarded as an outcome and not a mechanism of business model (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Patyal et al., 2022). In practical terms, this implies that prospective theory building must be more concerned with construct clarity, what will be considered an SBM (instead of operational greening), and what will be considered an I4.0 mechanism (instead of generic digitalization).

5.3. Citation impact versus network embeddedness: identifying "bridge" documents

The correlation between the number of citations and total link strength (TLS) presents significant dynamism: certain documents are not the most-cited classics but rather a medium of transition between otherwise disconnected ramifications of research. TLS is informative in the sense that it signifies the strength with which a document is embedded in the organization of other related publications in terms of its coupling or co-citation relationships (van Eck & Waltman, 2010). A document with a high TLS may or may not have the largest citation and can be viewed as a translation node, one that is repeatedly reused in clusters and thus influences cross-stream integration.

Regarding theory development, this means that the consolidation of the field does not rely solely on a limited number of seminal roadmaps (e.g., those focusing on I4.0–CE integration as a way of sustainable operations), but rather integrative works that seem to combine the themes of sustainability, digital transformation, and decision/implementation into a better managerial story (Jabbour et al., 2018; Okorie et al., 2018). Practically, high-TLS documents can be used to identify connector papers to be positioned and theory scaffolded by researchers, particularly in linking I4.0 technology mechanisms with business model-level constructs (value capture, revenue models, and ecosystem

governance).

5.4. Collaboration structure: growth with fragmentation, and why it matters

Co-authorship data is an indicator of a collaboration terrain with numerous localized clusters instead of one densely linked global community. This fragmentation is not new in rapidly expanding interdisciplinary areas but has consequences for theoretical convergence: fragmented collaboration is usually associated with parallel conceptual vocabularies and a recidivism of labelling similar mechanisms across domains (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

Regarding research programs, it is unsurprising that the literature may exhibit both high consensus as to broad mechanisms (for example, traceability facilitates circularity, and servitization facilitates lifecycle extension) and a lack of standardized operationalizations and similar empirical designs. Capability-based and twin transformation contributions, that is, skills, dynamic capabilities, and barriers to implementation, are of particular relevance in this case because they can provide cross-cutting constructs that can bring together studies in the fields of operations, strategy, and sustainability (Anshari and Ordóñez de Pablos, 2025; Buhler et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2024).

5.5. Geographic concentration and its interpretive caution

The trends in countries indicate that there are few major hubs with high international connections. However, one must not mistake bibliometric dominance by the concept of theory leadership: a large volume and significant collaboration power might be indicative of priorities in funding, institutional ability, and publication channels, but not of a conceptual breakthrough. In contrast, under-invented countries may still be able to have an oversized effect when their publications are framed as integrative, agenda-setting, or methodologically reusable.

This implies that uneven sectoral and regional coverage of the field could constitute a substantive component of its empirical foundation, a point often revisited in review articles that find a flaw in the lack of contextual diversity and more implementation-oriented data (Atif et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2021; Sahu et al., 2021). This is particularly relevant for SBM theory, as business model viability and value capture systems are sensitive to regulations, infrastructure, data governance regimes, and market maturity.

5.6. Theoretical contributions of this study

There are three main theoretical contributions presented in this paper based on the observed conceptual frame and the bibliometric structure. First, it reinvents Industry 4.0 (I4.0) as a business model capability substrate. Instead of positioning I4.0 technologies as individual solutions, the findings support the theorization of them as central capabilities, including connectivity, datafication, analytics, and automation, that precondition business model redesign (de Man and Strandhagen, 2017; Okorie et al., 2018). Second, the article elucidates the fundamental convergence processes in the field. The popularity of constructs of sustainability and circularity and I4.0 introduces a mechanism-based perspective, with digital servitization, lifecycle traceability, and supply-chain orchestration identified as the main connections between digital technologies and sustainable business model (SBM) deliverables (Atif et al., 2021; Jabbour et al., 2018; Patyal et al., 2022). Finally, the study identifies capabilities and governance as the integrative frontier. The fast pace of development in this field implies that future theoretical convergence will focus on the dynamics of capabilities, skill systems, and

inter-firm data governance. This transforms tech-to-sustainability performance into more complicated ability and governance frameworks that conduct scalable SBM performance (Anshari et al., 2025; Buhler et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2024).

5.7. Practical implications (managerial and policy-relevant)

From a practical perspective, the mapped structure implies that business model design is a first-order strategic decision that firms seeking I4.0-enabled transitions to sustainability must make. Customer relationship redesign is a key area that managers should consider because the blocks of customer-facing business models and partnerships in a circular economy and digital enablers fundamentally redesign them (Salvador et al., 2021). In addition, lifecycle data architecture, including traceability and condition monitoring investments, is no longer a matter of operational efficiency to provide new revenue models and secondary-market strategies at the core of circular business models (Jabbour et al., 2018; Okorie et al., 2018). Strong capability building is also a prerequisite to successfully mitigate this dual change; both skills and dynamic capabilities are conditions that must be developed to synchronize digital initiatives with the creation of sustainable value (Buhler et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2024). Finally, policymakers and standard-setting institutions should consider that, although digital transformation and circularity are closely linked, the governance of interoperability, data access, and accountability across value networks will become an essential factor in scaling circular business models out of the pilot phase.

5.8. Limitations relevant to interpreting the discussion

These discussion claims are particularly important in their interpretation in respect to two limitations. First, the analysis will be limited by Scopus coverage and metadata organization; therefore, some of the streams (e.g., practitioner outlets, non-indexed regional journals, etc.) might not be sufficiently represented. Second, bibliometric correlations are proxies: co-occurrence is not causal and co-citation is more of a similar practice of referencing than of agreement in theory (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017; van Eck and Waltman, 2010). The above theoretical inferences must, therefore, be considered grounded interpretations of the mapped form, rather than statements about the effectiveness of the mechanisms.

6. Conclusion, and Future Recommendations

This PRISMA-based bibliometric review which mapped the overlapping flows of research between Industry 4.0 and sustainable business models (Sustainable business models) through VOSviewer science- mapping methods. The dataset (391 Scopus-indexed journal articles) also suggests that the sphere is not only new but is growing fast, with the bulk of publications in 2021–2025 and a peak in 2025. At the source level, the findings indicate that the publication ecosystem is characterized by sustainability- and production-focused outlets, and Sustainability (Switzerland) is the most active outlet, while the Journal of Cleaner Production is the most central in terms of citation impact and centrality. The keyword structure validates the presence of a narrow conceptual core on Industry 4.0, sustainability/sustainable development, and circular economy, where digital transformation and business models are bridging concepts, in line with the perspective that digital technologies only become sustainability-relevant when they facilitate new value logics, including servitization, lifecycle traceability, and circular ecosystem coordination (Man and Strandhagen, 2017; Jabbour et al., 2018; Okorie et al., 2018). Document patterns also indicate that the influence is not solely based on the most

cited papers but is also structurally based on bridging papers, which have a high total link strength, and it is the structurally embedded integrative, cross-cluster nature of the field (van Eck and Waltman, 2010).

Future studies should move out of the technology catalogue and focus on explanatory and evaluative research to determine how Industry 4.0 capabilities can be converted into SBM results. Priorities for trackways are as follows: (1) comparative empirical research of I4.0-enabled circular business models (e.g., product-as-a-service and remanufacturing-led models) in different areas and industries; (2) more thorough theorization of the ecosystem and data governance as preconditions to platform-mediated circularity; and (3) the addition of dynamic capabilities and skills perspectives to explain the barriers to adoption and scaling in the field of the "twin transformation" exercise (Lu et al., 2024; Buhler et al., 2025). A multi-database triangulation and sensitivity of search strings should be included in future bibliometric studies to provide deeper coverage and boundary validity.

References

- Agrawal, R., Wankhede, V., Kumar, A., Luthra, S., & Huisingh, D. (2021). Progress and trends in integrating Industry 4.0 within Circular Economy: A comprehensive literature review and future research propositions. *Business Strategy and the Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2910>
- Alka, T., Raman, R., & Suresh, M. (2024). Research trends in innovation ecosystem and circular economy. *Discover Sustainability*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00535-5>
- ALSaoudi, T., Acquaye, A., Swarnakar, V., & Khalfan, M. (2026). Integration of Industry 4.0 with circular economy to enhance sustainable performance - a strategic framework. *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2026.101151>
- Anna, A., Mohamad, Z. Z., & Kumaran, V. V. (2025). DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY: BIBLIOMETRIC EVIDENCE FROM INDUSTRY 4.0. *Advanced International Journal of Business Entrepreneurship and SMEs*. <https://doi.org/10.35631/aijbes.726016>
- Anshari, M., & Pablos, P. O. de. (2025). Circular skillsets for the Fourth Industrial Revolution: optimising resource efficiency through technology and talent. *International Journal of Innovation Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijis-05-2024-0114>
- Atif, S. (2023). Analysing the alignment between circular economy and industry 4.0 nexus with industry 5.0 era: An integrative systematic literature review. *Sustainable Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2542>
- Atif, S., Ahmed, S., Wasim, M., Zeb, B., Pervez, Z., & Quinn, L. (2021). Towards a Conceptual Development of Industry 4.0, Servitisation, and Circular Economy: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU13116501>
- Bai, C., Orzes, G., & Sarkis, J. (2022). Exploring the impact of Industry 4.0 technologies on social sustainability through a circular economy approach. *Industrial Marketing Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2021.12.004>
- Bühler, L., Schuster, T., & Pflaum, A. (2025). TWIN TRANSFORMATION — THE CASE OF SMART CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIES: INSIGHTS FROM AN UMBRELLA REVIEW. *International*

- Journal of Innovation Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1142/s1363919625400079>
- Ćwiklicki, M., & Wojnarowska, M. (2020). Circular Economy and Industry 4.0: One-Way or Two-way Relationships? *Engineering Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.31.4.24565>
- Das, S., Bressanelli, G., & Saccani, N. (2024). Clustering the Research at the Intersection of Industry 4.0 Technologies, Environmental Sustainability and Circular Economy: Evidence from Literature and Future Research Directions. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, 4, 2473-2504-2473–2504. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-024-00393-3>
- Donthu, N., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, D., Pandey, N., & Lim, W. M. (2021). How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 133, 285–296.
- Ejsmont, K., Gładysz, B., & Kluczek, A. (2020). Industry 4.0 and Sustainability. *Unknown Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.32545/encyclopedia202007.0022.v2>
- Gorokhova, T., Kravchenko, M., Muterko, H., Korostova, I., & Lukash, M. (2024). Exploring the integration of circular economy and digitalization: current research progress and trends. *Revista Amazonia Investiga*. <https://doi.org/10.34069/ai/2024.73.01.25>
- Gupta, S., Singh, R., & Amrit, C. (2025). Integrating Industry 4.0 with Circular Economy Approach for Sustainable and Flexible Manufacturing Systems. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 26, 115-145-115–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-025-00438-y>
- Hadi, N. U., Almessabi, B., & Khan, M. I. (2025). Leveraging industry 4.0 and circular open innovation for digital sustainability: The role of circular ambidexterity. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2025.100545>
- Jabbour, A. B. L. D. S., Jabbour, C., Filho, M. G., & Roubaud, D. (2018). Industry 4.0 and the circular economy: a proposed research agenda and original roadmap for sustainable operations. *Annals of Operations Research*, 270, 273-286-273–286. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-018-2772-8>
- Khan, I., Ahmad, M., & Majava, J. (2021). Industry 4.0 and sustainable development: A systematic mapping of triple bottom line, Circular Economy and Sustainable Business Models perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.126655>
- Le-Dinh, T., Le, T. D., & Labelle, F. (2025). Digital technologies in the circular economy: a bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Trade Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jts-04-2025-0016>
- Lu, H., Zhao, G., & Liu, S. (2024). Integrating circular economy and Industry 4.0 for sustainable supply chain management: a dynamic capability view. *Production Planning & Control*, 35, 170-186-170–186. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2022.2063198>
- Man, J. C. de, & Strandhagen, J. (2017). An Industry 4.0 Research Agenda for Sustainable Business Models. *Procedia CIRP*, 63, 721-726-721–726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCIR.2017.03.315>
- Ng, T., Lau, S. Y., Ghobakhloo, M., Fathi, M., & Liang, M. (2022). The Application of Industry 4.0 Technological Constituents for Sustainable Manufacturing: A Content-

- Centric Review. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14074327>
- Nirmal, D., Gumte, K., & Sohal, A. (2025). Riding towards sustainable development in Industry 4.0: Learnings from a case of the bicycle manufacturing company. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2025.123970>
- Okorie, O., Salonitis, K., Charnley, F., Moreno, M., Turner, C., & Tiwari, A. (2018). Digitisation and the Circular Economy: A Review of Current Research and Future Trends. *Energies*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN11113009>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., & Brennan, S. E. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Bmj*, 372.
- Page, M. J., Moher, D., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., & Brennan, S. E. (2021). PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *Bmj*, 372.
- Patyal, V., Sarma, P., Modgil, S., Nag, T., & Dennehy, D. (2022). Mapping the links between Industry 4.0, circular economy and sustainability: a systematic literature review. *J. Enterp. Inf. Manag.*, 35, 1-35-1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeim-05-2021-0197>
- Polo, S., Rubio, E. M., Ayllón, J., & Agustina, B. de. (2025). Emerging Advances in Sustainable Manufacturing. *Processes*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr13051549>
- Sahu, A., Agrawal, S., & Kumar, G. (2021). Integrating Industry 4.0 and circular economy: a review. *J. Enterp. Inf. Manag.*, 35, 885-917-885–917. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeim-11-2020-0465>
- Salvador, R., Barros, M. V, Freire, F., Halog, A., Piekarski, C. M., & Francisco, A. C. de. (2021). Circular economy strategies on business modelling: Identifying the greatest influences. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 126918. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.126918>
- Shabur, Md. A. (2024). A comprehensive review on the impact of Industry 4.0 on the development of a sustainable environment. *Discover Sustainability*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00290-7>
- Silva, T. H. H. da, & Sehnem, S. (2022). The circular economy and Industry 4.0: synergies and challenges. *Revista de Gestão*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/rege-07-2021-0121>
- Strandhagen, J., Vallandingham, L. R., Fragapane, G., Strandhagen, J. W., Stangeland, A. B. H., & Sharma, N. (2017). Logistics 4.0 and emerging sustainable business models. *Advances in Manufacturing*, 5, 359-369-359–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S40436-017-0198-1>
- Van Eck, N., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523–538.
- Yadav, V., Gidwani, B. Das, & Nimawat, D. (2026). Assessment of cause-and-effect relationships among enablers of Sustainability 4.0 in the perspective of manufacturing industries. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-025-03381-9>